

Augmentation of Geospatial Embedding Models with Urban Morphometrics

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Abstract

Geospatial embeddings are an emerging method for translating the human geographic concept of "place" into quantitative vector representations of contiguous regions. However, existing approaches rely predominantly on point-of-interest (POI) counts as their primary input signal, omitting meaningful structural and morphological characteristics of urban form. We propose augmenting existing geospatial embedding methodologies with urban morphometrics, evaluated across three geospatial embedding models: CountEmbedder, ContextualCountEmbedder, and Hex2Vec. Using a pipeline that partitions study areas into H3 hexagonal cells and aggregates 46 morphometric features from OpenStreetMap data, we benchmark three input configurations (POI only, morphometrics only, and POI+morphometrics) on housing price and crime activity prediction tasks across King County, Chicago, and Philadelphia. Results indicate consistent accuracy gains from urban morphometrics, with the combined configuration winning reliably at resolution 9, more model- and city-dependent outcomes at resolution 8, and the largest gains accruing to count-based embedding models.

Keywords: geospatial embeddings, urban morphometrics, urban form representation

1. Introduction

The concept of "place" vs. "space" is a foundational but nebulous concept in human geography, and geographers have long struggled to translate it into objective, reproducible methodology (Tuan 1979; Kamruzzaman et al. 2025).

Geospatial embeddings represent a promising opportunity for more quantitative methodologies for modeling this concept. They are a method in which contiguous geographic regions are transformed into learned vector representations based on the presence, frequency, form, and configuration of semantic geographic features within them, and can be trained using a variety of machine learning

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algorithms. However, existing approaches frequently rely on POI counts as their primary input signal, which risks omitting meaningful structural and morphological characteristics of the regions being encoded.

We propose an improvement to the existing work on this subject via the inclusion of urban morphometrics into existing geospatial embedding models. Including urban morphometrics in the input feature space may yield a richer latent representation of place, enabling more precise implementation of downstream analysis tasks such as classification and site selection.

2. Related Work

A range of geospatial embedding methodologies have been developed and implemented within the "Spatial Representations for AI" (SRAI) library (Gramacki et al. 2023), a Python framework for partitioning study areas into micro-regions and learning vector representations of them. The simplest of these is CountEmbedder (CE), which represents each region as a vector of raw OSM tag-value counts. ContextualCountEmbedder (CCE) extends this by enriching each region's count vector with the aggregated tag-value counts of its surrounding hexagonal neighbourhood (Raczycki and Szymański 2021), so that the representation of a region reflects not only its own feature composition but also that of its immediate urban context. A more expressive example is Hex2Vec (Woźniak and Szymański 2021), which partitions the study area into a grid of H3 hexagonal cells and represents each cell as a vector of counts over a curated subset of OSM tag-value pairs. It trains a fully connected neural network using a skip-gram approach with negative sampling, where the model learns to distinguish true neighbouring region pairs from randomly sampled non-neighbouring ones, such that regions embedded in similar urban contexts are mapped to nearby points in the latent space. Like most models in this family, Hex2Vec draws its input features from tag-value counts sourced from OpenStreetMap (OSM), an approach which omits any direct information about urban form.

More recent work has extended embedding approaches to richer geometric inputs (Poly2Vec (Siampou et al. 2025), Geo2Vec (Chu and Shahabi 2026)), and a taxonomy of urban morphological patterns has been developed (Fleischmann et al. 2026). However, urban morphometrics have not yet been systematically integrated into the embedding pipelines listed above.

A related line of work has demonstrated that combining such vector-based embeddings with satellite imagery embeddings downstream can substantively improve performance on socioeconomic prediction tasks (Choudhury et al. 2025). Augmenting with urban morphometrics may achieve a comparable enrichment of the input feature space without introducing an additional and often costly imagery modality, since the morphometric signal is derived directly from comparatively more accessible vector GIS data.

3. Methodology

We implement a pipeline¹ that partitions the study area into H3 hexagonal cells, computes a set of urban morphometrics from OpenStreetMap data using the momepy library (Fleischmann 2019), and aggregates the results at the cell level. To assess the contribution of urban morphometrics to embedding quality, we evaluate three models from the SRAI library (Gramacki et al. 2023), namely CountEmbedder, ContextualCountEmbedder, and Hex2Vec, across three input feature configurations: POI counts only, urban morphometrics only, and a combined POI + urban morphometrics setting.

3.1. Urban Morphometrics

The momepy library provides a unified interface through which urban morphometrics can be computed on buildings, land parcels, and transportation networks. From momepy’s full catalogue, 46 metrics were selected that together provide a comprehensive characterization of urban form across the following categories: building dimension, building shape, building distribution and configuration, building intensity, street relationship and street network connectivity (per-node and graph-level). The full list with implementation details is provided in Appendix I. *Figure 1* depicts the generation of selected metrics available through momepy.

Figure 1: Visual representation of selected momepy morphometric measures for a single building footprint (black, left). The footprint is transformed to a series of metrics (right), such as its perimeter wall length (red), longest axis length (cyan), circular compactness (green) and various comparisons to its neighbouring buildings (black dashed lines). Basemap © OpenStreetMap Contributors.

Most metrics are computed per geographic feature and aggregated to the regional level using a set of statistical summaries: mean, median, standard deviation, and a configurable number of quantiles. Some metrics require spatial context beyond the region boundary, such as the immediate neighbourhood of a building. These are computed using a buffer around the region, retaining only

1. Code available at: <https://github.com/iboates/geospatial-embeddings-urban-morphometrics>

values for features that intersect the region itself. Certain building metrics are computed at two scales: per individual building footprint, and per dissolved structure formed by adjacent joined buildings. Transport network metrics are computed on both a vehicle-centric and a pedestrian-centric graph. A small number of momepy metrics were re-implemented with custom logic. The urban morphometric features are then concatenated with POI counts to form the input feature vectors for the combined configuration.

3.2. Evaluation

To assess the impact of urban morphometrics on representation learning and compare it with embeddings derived solely from POI counts, we adopt a two-fold evaluation strategy combining a qualitative analysis with a quantitative benchmark on downstream tasks.

We first conduct a qualitative analysis aimed at illustrating the complementarity between POI-based and morphometric feature families. We manually select pairs of H3 cells exhibiting near-identical POI counts but visibly contrasting urban morphologies. For each pair, we inspect the corresponding POI counts and the morphometric descriptors, in order to assess whether and how the latter discriminate between cells that POI-based representations would otherwise conflate.

For the quantitative evaluation, we follow the Open Benchmark for Spatial Representation (OBSR) (Moska et al. 2025), a set of evaluations on downstream tasks. We focus on region-based tasks such as crime activity prediction (CAP) and housing price prediction (HPP). We use the fixed train-test stratified split, with 10% of the training set held out for validation.

Unlike CE and CCE, which are count-based models requiring no training, Hex2Vec is trained on the training set prior to evaluation. The resulting embeddings are then used as input features for a downstream model, trained on the training set with early stopping on the validation set. We report Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) as our primary metrics. For each experimental configuration, we perform 10 runs and report the mean on the test set.

4. Results

4.1. Qualitative Analysis

To illustrate what morphometric features contribute beyond POI-based representations, we examine two representative pairs of H3 (resolution 8) cells in King County, Washington.

Figure 2 depicts two regions that are indicated as being very similar when only considering the overall POI counts, while their urban morphometric profiles show a stark difference, particularly in their median building rectangularity (0.996 on the left versus 0.773 on the right), and the median node degree in the local pedestrian networks (1 on the left versus 3 on the right). To generalize, the left region has buildings that are more consistently rectangular than the right region, and the right region has a more densely connected pedestrian network. Visual inspection supports these distinctions as well, with the left taking the form of a typical rural North American countryside

landscape comprised of single-dwelling homes with simple rectangular footprints, while the right takes the form of a dense and highly pedestrian-accessible complex of buildings which take a more complex, non-rectangular form.

Figure 2: A representative pair of H3 cells at resolution 8 in King County (Washington, USA) with similar POI counts but different morphometric features. Both cells have around the same amount of buildings and a forest while having different median building rectangularity and pedestrian network connectivity. Left: cell 8828d4aca1fffff. Right: cell 8828d4af17fffff. Source data © OpenStreetMap Contributors.

Figure 3 shows two regions which are again indicated as being extremely similar according to the cosine similarity of their Hex2Vec embeddings when using default OSM tag selection (0.97). Visual inspection alone shows an obvious difference in the overall urban profile of the regions, with the left in the form of a typical North American single-dwelling suburban landscape, while the right is a much denser, grid-like, inner-city configuration. The embeddings produced by Hex2Vec with only urban morphometric features, however, change the cosine similarity drastically to -0.61 . An inspection of the largest morphometric differences shows a 100th-percentile shared wall ratio value of 0.00 on the left and 0.59 on the right, street profile openness values of 0.52 (50th percentile) and 0.70 (75th percentile) on the left, compared with 0.83 and 1.00 on the right. Finally, there is a 25th-percentile pedestrian network node degree of 3 on the left and 1 on the right, which may seem counter-intuitive due to the “downtown nature” of the right region, but there is also a clear dedicated pedestrian network present in the left region, increasing its overall connectivity.

4.2. Quantitative Benchmark

The results across all three datasets, summarized in *Tables 1, 2, and 3*, indicate that integrating urban morphometric data into existing geospatial embedding methodologies consistently improves downstream regression and prediction accuracy, with the magnitude of improvement varying by model, dataset, and resolution.

The most pronounced gains were observed on the King County HPP task (*Table 1*), particularly for CE and CCE, where the combined “POI + urban morphometrics” embeddings were the top performers at both resolutions. Urban morphometric features capture detailed building-level characteristics, such as footprint area, shape, and relative configuration that are inherently strong predictors of property value and are largely absent from POI-based representations alone, which likely

Figure 3: A representative pair of H3 cells at resolution 8 in King County (Washington, USA) with highly similar Hex2Vec POI only embeddings (0.97 cosine similarity) but dissimilar Hex2Vec Urban Morphology only embeddings (-0.61 cosine similarity). Left: cell 8828d426bdf5fff. Right: cell 8828d55315fff. Source data © OpenStreetMap Contributors.

accounts for the magnitude of the gains observed here. Hex2Vec benefited more modestly, which may reflect the fact that its embedding size remains fixed regardless of input features, while CE and CCE produce larger embeddings when additional features are included, though further analysis would be needed to confirm this. The one exception to the “POI + urban morphometrics” dominance occurred at resolution 8 for Hex2Vec, where “urban morphometrics only” outperformed the combined variant.

Table 1: Performance of different embedding models on House Sales in King County dataset at resolutions 8 and 9 and feature configurations.

Model	Metric	Res 8			Res 9		
		POI	Morpho	POI+M	POI	Morpho	POI+M
Hex2Vec	MAE $\times 10^4$	16.38	13.43	14.81	11.87	11.66	11.08
	MAPE (%)	32.74	26.74	29.22	25.26	25.17	23.49
CCE	MAE $\times 10^4$	21.93	12.53	9.90	12.62	10.83	9.73
	MAPE (%)	42.59	26.29	21.01	25.77	23.30	21.07
CE	MAE $\times 10^4$	25.64	12.91	11.36	12.82	11.83	11.43
	MAPE (%)	49.74	27.21	24.39	26.95	25.45	24.34

On the Chicago CAP task (Table 2), the picture is split between resolutions. At resolution 9 the “POI + urban morphometrics” configuration wins across all three embedder families on both MAE and R^2 , mirroring the dataset-wide pattern observed for King County and Philadelphia at the same scale. At resolution 8, however, the best configuration depends on the model: Hex2Vec prefers the combined variant, CCE is most accurate with POI features alone, and CE is essentially a three-way tie, with “urban morphometrics only” marginally ahead on MAE and the combined variant marginally ahead on R^2 . The cross-model disagreement at resolution 8 contrasts with Philadelphia, where all three models converge on “urban morphometrics only” at the same resolution, indicating that the relative informativeness of urban form versus POIs is not a fixed property of the spatial

scale but interacts with city-specific characteristics.

Table 2: Performance of different embedding models on Chicago Crime Activity dataset at resolutions 8 and 9 and feature configurations.

Model	Metric	Res 8			Res 9		
		POI	Morpho	POI+M	POI	Morpho	POI+M
Hex2Vec	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	4.71	4.21	4.14	3.05	2.89	2.76
	R^2	0.51	0.38	0.62	0.37	0.38	0.44
CCE	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	3.55	4.04	3.76	2.61	2.73	2.42
	R^2	0.74	0.56	0.69	0.54	0.45	0.57
CE	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	4.30	4.00	4.35	2.98	2.76	2.59
	R^2	0.57	0.59	0.59	0.45	0.39	0.58

On the Philadelphia CAP task (Table 3), the dominant pattern inverts depending on the resolution. At resolution 8, “urban morphometrics only” was the top configuration across all three embedder families, beating both “POI only” and the combined “POI + urban morphometrics” variant by a substantial margin. Adding POI features to morphometric ones not only failed to help but consistently degraded performance, suggesting that at the neighbourhood scale of resolution 8 cells, the urban form signal is a determining factor. At resolution 9 the picture reverts to the “POI + urban morphometrics” dominance seen on the King County task: the combined variant is best for CCE and CE on both MAE and R^2 , and best for Hex2Vec on MAE. The cross-resolution flip is consistent across embedder families, which suggests it reflects a property of the dataset and spatial scale rather than a quirk of any particular model: at coarser cells morphometric structure carries the predictive signal on its own, while at finer cells the POI distribution becomes informative enough that combining the two pays off.

Table 3: Performance of different embedding models on Philadelphia Crime Activity dataset at resolutions 8 and 9 and feature configurations.

Model	Metric	Res 8			Res 9		
		POI	Morpho	POI+M	POI	Morpho	POI+M
Hex2Vec	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	5.07	3.94	4.58	3.13	3.19	3.04
	R^2	0.46	0.66	0.55	0.37	0.34	0.35
CCE	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	4.99	3.76	4.44	2.97	3.11	2.83
	R^2	0.23	0.71	0.48	0.42	0.32	0.44
CE	MAE $\times 10^{-2}$	5.14	3.89	4.63	3.07	3.16	2.96
	R^2	0.19	0.66	0.48	0.37	0.35	0.41

5. Discussion

While urban morphometrics demonstrably improve performance on several downstream tasks, their inclusion introduces a number of limitations and open questions worth discussing.

First, computing and aggregating morphometric features for large study areas requires substantial computational resources, adding to the already considerable overhead of loading and processing OSM data. In practice, this pipeline cost may represent a barrier to adoption, particularly for large-scale or resource-constrained applications.

Second, the generalization of morphometric-augmented embeddings to unseen regions remains an open question. While improvements are observed within the cities used in this study, it is unclear whether these would hold when transferring models to new cities or regions without retraining. Urban morphology varies considerably across geographic and cultural contexts, and metrics calibrated on one urban typology may not carry equivalent meaning elsewhere.

Third, several urban morphometrics are sensitive to mapping conventions and data availability, a limitation that applies to any morphometric-based method. When the same city is represented by different data sources, or when OSM coverage varies across regions, differences in the mapping style of building footprints and transportation networks can affect metric values and undermine cross-regional comparability. Some metrics may also be effectively meaningless in the absence of necessary attribute data and should be excluded from training in such cases. The volume metric, for instance, requires that the vast majority of building footprints carry accurate height information, which is rarely the case outside of thoroughly mapped areas. For this reason, we excluded it from our feature set.

6. Conclusion

This work demonstrated that augmenting POI-based geospatial embeddings with urban morphometric features improves downstream prediction accuracy, though the form of the improvement varies by spatial resolution, embedding model, and city. Gains were most consistent at resolution 9, where the combined “POI + urban morphometrics” configuration was the top performer across all three datasets and all three embedder families. At resolution 8 the picture was more variable: morphometric features dominated on Philadelphia, the combined configuration dominated on King County, and Chicago showed a model-dependent split, suggesting that the relative informativeness of urban form versus POI signals is not a fixed property of spatial scale but interacts with city-specific characteristics. Across datasets, gains were stronger for CountEmbedder and ContextualCountEmbedder than for Hex2Vec, which we attribute to the latter’s fixed embedding size, and the most substantial improvements were observed on the King County housing price prediction task, where detailed building-level characteristics proved to be strong complementary predictors of property value.

Realizing these gains in practice remains subject to the limitations discussed above, namely the computational cost of feature extraction, sensitivity to OSM data quality, and open questions around cross-regional generalization. Future work should address these barriers while exploring adaptive embedding architectures that can better exploit morphometric inputs, and investigating which morphometric features carry the strongest predictive signal as a function of spatial resolution and urban context.

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Appendix I. Full Catalogue of Computed Metrics

The following table lists the full set of 46 urban morphometrics used as input features in this work. For each metric, the table indicates whether it is natively available in momepy or re-implemented with custom logic, whether it requires neighbourhood context beyond the region boundary, whether it is computed at both the individual building and joined building structure scales, and whether it is already spatially aggregate and therefore requires no further aggregation step.

#	Metric	Present in Momepy	Custom implementation	Neighbourhood context	Building + joined building structures	Already aggregate
Building Dimension Metrics						
1	courtyard.area	✓	✓	✓		
2	floor.area	✓	✓			
3	longest.axis.length	✓				
4	perimeter.wall ¹	✓	✓		✓	
Building Shape Metrics						
5	centroid.corner.distance	✓			✓	
6	circular.compactness	✓				
7	compactness.weighted.axis	✓			✓	
8	convexity	✓				
9	corners	✓				
10	courtyard.index	✓		✓		
11	elongation	✓				
12	equivalent.rectangular.index	✓				
13	facade.ratio	✓			✓	
14	form.factor	✓				
15	fractal.dimension	✓			✓	
16	rectangularity	✓				
17	shape.index	✓				
18	square.compactness	✓				
19	squareness	✓				
Building Distribution and Configuration Metrics						
20	alignment	✓		✓		
21	building.adjacency	✓		✓		
22	cell.alignment	✓		✓		
23	mean.interbuilding.distance	✓		✓		
24	neighbor.distance	✓		✓		
25	neighbors	✓		✓		
26	orientation	✓				
27	shared.walls	✓		✓		
28	street.alignment	✓		✓		
Building Intensity and Street Relationship Metrics						
29	courtyards	✓	✓	✓		✓
30	nearest.street.distance	✓	✓	✓		
31	street.profile	✓		✓		

Continued on next page

Table 4 (continued)

#	Metric	Present in Momepy	Custom implementation	Neighbourhood context	Building + joined building structures	Already aggregate
Street Network Connectivity Metrics (Per-Node)²						
32	betweenness_centrality	✓		✓		
33	closeness_centrality	✓		✓		
34	clustering	✓		✓		
35	cyclomatic	✓		✓		
36	degree	✓		✓		
37	edge_node_ratio	✓		✓		
38	gamma	✓		✓		
39	mean_node_degree	✓		✓		
40	mean_node_dist	✓		✓		
41	meshedness	✓		✓		
42	straightness_centrality	✓		✓		
Street Network Connectivity Metrics (Graph-Level)²						
43	cds_length_total	✓		✓		✓
44	gamma_global	✓		✓		✓
45	meshedness_global	✓		✓		✓
46	proportion ³	✓		✓		✓

¹ `perimeter_wall` emits one column per raw building (`_individual` suffix) and one per dissolved structure (`_joined` suffix).

² All 15 street connectivity metrics are computed twice: once on the directed vehicle street graph and once on the undirected pedestrian graph.

³ `proportion` emits three output columns: `proportion_three` (T-junctions), `proportion_four` (cross-roads), and `proportion_dead` (dead-ends).